

PHILOSOPHICAL AND PSYCHOLOGICAL VIEWS ON THE DEVELOPMENT OF CRITICAL AND LOGICAL THINKING TO STUDENTS OF THE NON-PHILOLOGICAL DIRECTION

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Abstract. *This article talks about philosophical and psychological point-of-view theories in the development of critical and logical thinking. It also enumerates the division of such thinking into several types. Alternatively, several scholars have cited opinions on the subject.*

Keywords: *L.Elder and R.Paul, logic, critical thinker, A.Avloni, education of thought, Socrates, K.Popper, W.M.Bryushinkin.*

The demand of the 21st century assumes the development of new methods and methods of educating independent-minded competent individuals, improving the provision of knowledge in the process of teaching students and working with them. For this reason, it requires students to avoid monotony in the sense that teaching methods are diverse in order to broaden their worldview, moving towards thinking, research and a clear goal. One of the similar technologies is the formation of critical thinking skills of students in communicative communication. It is no secret that through critical thinking, a person develops such important characteristics as being able to think freely, analyze, compare, specialise, be able to defend his own thoughts, strive for innovations, as well as being able to think logically, self-awareness, communicative literacy, feeling elegance and beauty in being, being able to enjoy it, being both mentally and physically healthy, absorbing national values. Critical thinking may also refer to, ensures that students are able to profoundly master and practice the knowledge given. To achieve such a result, it is important to project the purpose of the lesson under study on the basis of clear, pedagogical technology. In humanity, the trait of curiosity has existed since birth and tries to know what is in existence, to reflect on them. It is this characteristic of curiosity that develops the human mind, and in this way adventures and discoveries occur. The desire to know and understand what is in existence, in turn, develops the ability to think critically. The importance of critical thinking in teaching English is invaluable, and one of the tasks of Foreign Language teachers is the development of this ability. Foreign distinguished scientists

L.Elder and R.Paul has commented on critical thinking as follows: the ability of individuals to manage their own thinking and develop appropriate criteria and standards for analyzing their own thoughts is called critical thinking. Another scholar, W.In Maiorana's view, critical thinking can be called a process that focuses on understanding, evaluating, problem - solving solutions to different views. In general, skills such as observation, analysis, interpretation, reflection, assessment, inference, explanation, problem solving, and decision making are necessary to be able to think critically. Therefore, educators should organize classes to honor such problems.

Logic is derived from the Latin "logos" meaning "thought", "word", "mind", "speech", "law". It has been described by middle and Middle Eastern thinkers as a "Libra that distinguishes genuine thought from falsehood." In particular, Abu Homid Ghazzali's "Al-qustas al-mustaqim" described logic as "the right balance". In the middle age, European logicians, on the other hand, described logic as a "way of making discoveries", in contrast to Eastern thinkers. The science of logic can be called "propedeutics", that is, the science that prepares the study of other sciences, the reason is the role of the science of abstract logic in the system of Sciences and the issues it studies in it. Logic itself is also divided into 3 types according to its orientation: formal, dialectical, mathematical.

Critical thinking is derived from the Greek word "krikto" meaning "criticism", "assessment", "confession". This means that the term is ambiguous-not to blame someone either for an event, but to use mental capacity to express an objective opinion

of situations and events. In other words, thinking that provides the ability to take its position on the issue under discussion and justify it, the ability to listen to the interlocutor, carefully consider his arguments and analyze their logic. "A critical thinker is someone who uses certain criteria to assess feedback, form positions, and make decisions."(Sherry Diestler, 2009.)

Thinking is actually a natural process that lasts from the moment a person is born until he dies. Through thinking, a person analyzes the information that exists or is being given, finds a solution and decides. The spiritual-human quality that constitutes the activity of a person, the strength, the power of his self is thinking. Its development also drives socio-economic progress. From the earliest times since the creation of man, thought has served as an important factor for the awareness of phenomena in nature and their use for living and for self-preservation. In this way, gradually a person's ability to think developed, and other material and spiritual manifestations of human labor began to appear. Thinking is the interconnection and development of meanings in the human brain, which consists of several stages (awareness, observation, awareness, thinking). There are several types of thinking, such as chronological, problematic, hypothetical, heuristic, intrusive. In general, when we systemize types of thinking, cause and effect are divided into logical thinking. The great Uzbek pedagogue A. Avlonius commented on the upbringing of thought: the most necessary in the upbringing of thought says that it is a sacred task that has been appreciated and has come since many times, relying on the attention of teachers, imposed on their conscience. The power, elegance, breadth of thought depends on the upbringing of the teacher. With the lesson, the two are not separated, the body of one is located on one. The effect of education given is inevitable to be low if children do not learn to think freely. From these words, we can conclude that humanity must know, understand, have a high intelligence and experience of being in order to conduct its life and activities in a meaningful way. Only then can a person realize such characteristics as thoughtful thought, truthfulness, correctness, non-falling into

the singing of lust. Unprecedented innovations in modern education encourage pedagogical workers to work more intensively on themselves. If we take critical thinking from the psychological side and age it, we have divided the thinking capacity of humans into several types. These are:

- * Deductive reasoning
- * Inductive reasoning
- * Analytical thinking
- * Investigative thinking
- * Systematic thinking
- * Creative thinking
- * Synthesis of thinking
- Interrogative fiction
- Different thinking
- Convergent thinking
- Synvergent thinking
- Conceptual thinking
- * Metaphorical thinking
- Traditional thinking
- Critical thinking

In this scientific work I will give information on the study of critical and logical thinking, both philosophical and psychological. Critical thinking is, in essence, a process based on the analysis, understanding and evaluation of information, situations. In other words, the process of critical thinking refers to thinking equal to a higher level in relation to the process of traditional thinking. A person with such an ability looks at, analyzes and evaluates incoming information with Shubha, without simply receiving it directly. In order for civilization to occur in a society, it is necessary for members of that society to have the ability to think critically and through it the origin of logical thinking. Critical thinking is also about making the right decisions about what to do in general. In a word, it means "to evaluate information correctly". There are many useful aspects of critical thinking. Including: This is the ability to think in general. The lack of critical and logical thinking easily evokes an increase in the number of receivers, like a human, in which various false, harmful, information negatively affects the consciousness of people, and later also their personal life. People with critical thinking skills will have the following traits:

- Being able to base their beliefs and values

- Being able to understand the logical connections between ideas
- To be able to determine the relevance of ideas
- * Systematic problem solving
- * Identification of discrepancies and errors in thinking

The academic discipline of philosophy focuses on the discovery of truth and writing. Socrates, Plato, Aristotle and others express a philosophical approach to criticism thinking. Socrates led the process of thinking about thinking in a new direction methodically questioning and analyzing universal themes (Daniel & Auric, 2011). Plato shifted when he formed a "clear Union" - a line on the concept of philosophy-between knowledge (Epistema) and adults, and between faith (doxa) and childhood" (Daniel & Auric, 2011, p.2011). 417). Aristotle developed the rules of formal logic to better define the basis for the reflection of universal concepts and the development of a philosophy of good thinking towards high-order thinking (Daniel and Auric, 2011, p.2011). 417). The works of these philosophers laid the foundation for the philosophical approach of 'good thinking', but it was not the only one academic discipline that studied critical thinking. Found in psychology the cognitive psychological approach differs from the philosophical one.

In the current era of globalization, it is very easy to find information about any topic on the internet. But the main problem is that we are able to find the necessary and correct information. Having such a right choice requires a person to critically study knowledge and diligence on the subject, and at the same time correct and incorrect information. Our honourable President SH.M. It is advisable for us to remember the following sentences of Mirziyoyev: "critical analysis, strict discipline and personal responsibility should be the Daily rule of the activities of each leader."

In the middle of the 20th century, the concept of "critical thinking" entered the science of pedagogy, and the term was first coined by K.Popper used. K.According to Popper, each living soul acts as a "solver" of problems.The data in existence presupposes the crash as confirmation or rejection of the meaning of a living organism.Critical thinking is used in such

a situation as a way to search for truth and eliminate error. Working in this direction, brogan became a well-known traitor (J. Denmark, M. Lipman, D. Halpern, D. Clowes, E. De Bono) argues that critical thinking is reflexive in nature and learns from a person his own thinking and its correctness.

The Complete classification of critical thinking.The use of cognitive techniques, which Halpern gave, in his opinion, increases the likelihood of achieving the desired final result, is critical thinking. That is, the type of thinking used to control,justify, solve problems,draw conclusions, make probabilistic assessments and make decisions is called critical thinking. V.M.Bryushinkin concretized the concept, describing critical thinking as a directed mind action sequence.

R.Paul has come to the following hulosas about critical thinking in his scientific research: critical thinking is thinking about the thought process, which arises where it is necessary to clearly state the thought and develops in a continuous way.It took shape as the basis of the educational changes of the 21st century.A.V.Tygalo and T.S.According to varapai's views, the information revolution is observed not only in technology - technology, but also in human thought. The current personality has the ability to critically analyze incoming information flows. This is not only the ability, but also the mechanism of adaptation to society. A specific type of mental activity that allows a person to express common sense about the thought proposed is critical thinking, Johnson described.V.M.Bryushinkin concretized this view by saying:critical thinking is a sequence of directed mental actions.Sorina G.V. highly appreciating the process of critical thinking, this process includes the ability to think at the scientific level, work with questions, judgments,conclusions,developed methods of logical thinking.The connection of critical thinking with the psychology of communication and personality was first emphasized by Noel-Tsigulskaya. The aspect of studying critical thinking from the point of view of the development of the ability to think critically is an important importance of pedagogy and the science of psychology.M. Lipmen identified,

compared and came to such a conclusion the differences of everyday and critical thinking, according to which critical thinking is highly valued, the reason is that critical thinking is a clear expression of meaningful and logical thoughts.

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